

THE CONDENSATION OF α -SUBSTITUTED ACETOACETATES WITH PHENOLS.
PART VIII. THE CONDENSATION OF C-ALKYL-RESORCINOLS AND
ETHYLPYROGALLOL WITH ETHYL ACETOSUCCINATE.

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The condensation of C-alkyl-resorcinols and ethyl pyrogallol with ethyl acetosuccinate has been described. Various coumarin-3-acetic acids derived from the above phenols and their derivatives have been obtained.

In continuation of our investigations on the reactivity of ethyl acetosuccinate in its Pechmann condensation described in the preceding parts of this series (Parts VI and VII), the present work was undertaken in order to synthesise coumarin-3-acetic acids from C-alkyl-resorcinols and to study the reactivity of the above ester in its Pechmann reaction with C-alkyl-resorcinols.

The condensation of 4-ethylresorcinol with ethyl acetosuccinate in presence of sulphuric acid proceeds smoothly and the product obtained is ethyl 7-hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate (I, R=Et), m.p. 184-85°, the course of reaction being represented below :

The ester (I, R=Et) is hydrolysed to the corresponding coumarin-3-acetic acid. This acid is stable and attempts to decarboxylate it are unsuccessful.

Similarly, 4-methyl-, 4-propyl-, 4-butyl-resorcinols are condensed and the products obtained are ethyl 7-hydroxy-6-alkyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate (I; R=Me, Pr, Bu) and the corresponding acids have been obtained by hydrolysis.

All the condensation products dissolve in alkali with blue fluorescence characteristic of 7-hydroxycoumarin derivatives. To study the effect of the change of the condensing agent, sulphuric acid has been substituted by phosphorus oxychloride. In all cases, the condensation in the presence of the oxychloride proceeds easily at ordinary temperature even without a solvent, the identical coumarins being obtained in far greater yields.

The behaviour of 4-ethylpyrogallol is similar to that of 4-ethylresorcinol; it condenses smoothly with ethyl acetosuccinate in presence of phosphorus oxychloride giving an excellent yield of ethyl 7:8-dihydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate.

It is seen from the above that the condensation is effected as easily as in case of unsubstituted resorcinol and pyrogallol. The alkyl group in 4-position of the resorcinol and pyrogallol nucleus has practically very little or no retarding influence on the course of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl 7-Hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate.—4-Ethylresorcinol required for this work was prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of resacetophenone using the modified method of Robinson and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1494).

(i) 4-Ethylresorcinol (2.5 g.) was mixed with ethyl acetosuccinate (4 g.) and sulphuric acid (80%, 10 c.c.) slowly added with cooling. The mixture was then left overnight and worked up by adding into ice-cold water; the solid was collected, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol as fine plates, m.p. 183-84°, yield 2 g.

(ii) The above condensation was carried out in presence of phosphorus oxychloride (2 c.c.). Next day the mixture was treated with water; the solid crystallised from alcohol as fine plates, yield 4g., m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above sample, 185°. (Found: C, 65.7; H, 6.6. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 66.2; H, 6.2 per cent). The coumarin is soluble in acetic acid, hot alcohol, benzene and chloroform; insoluble in petroleum ether. It gives bright blue fluorescence in alkali solution and in concentrated sulphuric acid.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by acetic anhydride and a drop of sulphuric acid, crystallised from alcohol as fine crystals, m.p. 146-47°. (Found: C, 64.95; H, 6.1. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 65.1; H, 6.02 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative, prepared by benzoyl chloride in presence of pyridine, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 123°. (Found: C, 69.42; H, 5.5. $C_{22}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 5.6 per cent).

The *methoxy* derivative, prepared by dimethyl sulphate in cold, crystallised from dilute alcohol as clusters of needles, m.p. 93-94°. (Found: C, 66.85; H, 6.7. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.58 per cent).*

Hydrolysis of the Ester.—The ester (1g.) was treated with *αN*-sodium hydroxide (25 c.c.) for about half an hour on a steam-bath. It was cooled, acidified and the solid crystallised from dilute acetic acid as needles, m.p. 221-22°. (Found: C, 64.4; H, 5.2. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.22; H, 5.34 per cent). The acid is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid, sparingly so in boiling water and insoluble in benzene, chloroform and petroleum ether.

The *acetyl*, *benzoyl* and *anilide* crystallised from alcohol, melting respectively at 209°, 160° and 257°.

Ethyl 7-Hydroxy-6-propyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate.—4-Propyl-resorcinol was prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of resorpiophenone (Chakravarti and Chakravarty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 148).

The resorcinol (2 g.), mixed with ethyl acetosuccinate (3 g.), was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) with cooling. It was then worked up as before. The solid was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water. It was crystallised from alcohol as thin rectangular plates, m.p. 169-70°, yield 1.5 g.

The condensation was studied with phosphorus oxychloride (2 c.c.) as condensing agent and worked up as before. The product was crystallised from rectified spirit as clusters of needles, m.p. 170°, yield about 4 g. (Found: C, 67.9; H, 7.0. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.6 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 100°-101°. (Found: C, 65.7; H, 6.1. $C_{19}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 65.9; H, 6.36 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as rhombic crystals, m.p. 115-16°. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 5.4. $C_{22}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9 per cent).

The *methoxy* derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 94-95°.

Hydrolysis.—The 6-propylcoumarin-ester was hydrolysed as before; the acid obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 199-200°. (Found: C, 61.6; H, 6.4. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4 \cdot H_2O$ requires C, 61.3; H, 6.13 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 203°.

The *methoxy* derivative (obtained in course of the methylation of the ester due to hydrolysis) crystallised from dilute acetic acid as short needles, m.p. 176°; (Found: C, 66.0; H, 5.9. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 66.2; H, 6.2 per cent).

Ethyl 7-Hydroxy-6-butyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate.—4-Butylresorcinol was prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of resbutyropheneone.

4-Butyl resorcinol (2 g.), ethyl aceto-succinate (2.5 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (3 c.c.) were carefully mixed and kept as before. On working up as before, the product was crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 165-66°. (Found: C, 67.7; H, 7.45. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 67.93; H, 6.92 per cent).

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 116-17°. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 7.3. $C_{20}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 66.7; H, 6.7 per cent).

The benzoyl derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 124°. (Found: C, 71.22; H, 6.05. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 71.1; H, 6.16 per cent).

The methoxy derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 88°.

Hydrolysis.—The above ester was hydrolysed as before. The acid crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 205°. (Found: Equiv., 288.5. $C_{14}H_{16}O_4$ requires Equiv., 290).

The methoxy derivative, obtained by hydrolysing the methoxy ester obtained above, crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 160°. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 6.3. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 65.2; H, 6.7 per cent).

Ethyl 7-Hydroxy-4:6-dimethylcoumarin-3-acetate.—4-Methylresorcinol, m.p. 105°, was prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of β -resorcyaldehyde. It is interesting to note in this connection that different specimens of 4-methylresorcinol obtained by different workers are reported to melt at various temperatures ranging from 83-105°. (cf. Clemmensen, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 51).

4-Methylresorcinol (0.5 g.) was condensed in presence of phosphorus oxychloride (1 c.c.) as before. The product was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 163-84°. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent).

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 168-169°. (Found: C, 64.1; H, 5.7. $C_{17}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 64.15; H, 5.66 per cent).

Ethyl 7:8-Dihydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate.—4-Ethylpyrogallol was prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of gallacetophenone ("Organic Synthesis", XIV, 40). 4-Ethyl pyrogallol (3 g.), the ester (4.5 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (3 c.c.) were mixed with cooling in ice. The solid obtained after treatment with water was washed with little acetic acid to remove coloured impurities. The colourless solid obtained was first crystallised from acetone-ligroin mixture and then from benzene as soft silky needles, m.p. 150-51°; yield 3 g. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 62.74; H, 5.9 per cent). The coumarin dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with orange colour and in sodium hydroxide with lemon-yellow colour. It gives green colour with ferric chloride.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 149° mixed m.p. with the original substance depressed to 130-32°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 5.8. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 61.54; H, 5.64 per cent).

The benzoyl derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 163°.

Hydrolysis.—The ester (1 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (1 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) added and the mixture refluxed on a steam-bath for nearly 3 hours. On cooling the solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 275°. (Found: Equiv., 280.1. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires Equiv., 278).

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 153.54°. (Found: C, 59.6; H, 5.1. $C_{22}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 59.7; H, 5.0 per cent).

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